

OVERCOMING FROM ACADEMIC STRESS FOR HAPPY AND JOYOUS STUDENTS**Dr. S.K. Sharma**

Ph. D. Guide

*Department of Library & Information Science,
Veer Narmad South Gujarat University, Surat.***Ms. Meena S. Suryavanshi**

Librarian,

*St. Xavier's Institute of Education, Mumbai.***Abstract –**

There are problems everywhere for students-problems at home with their parents and siblings, problems in the educational institute, with their friends and education. Adolescent is the stage where a person begins to mature. At this stage stress can be effective. At adolescent, a person may have stress due to many reason such as early puberty, peer pressure, substance abuse and identity crisis. Stress affects the physical and behavioural level. A person needs to know that this stage there are many changes and if there is no help they experience stress. This paper is the analysis of Academic stress from 2016 to 2020. A lot can be done by the Educational institutes administration to choke out the stress among their students if they try and implement.

Key words – *Adolescence, Academic stress; Stress coping strategies, Student's stress, family; Educational institutes support, Health, An Intervention Teacher.*

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Introduction –

Arnold(1960) defines, “Stress is any condition that disturbs normal functioning”.

Lazarus(1966) defines, “Stress refers to physiological, behavioral and cognitive responses to events appraised as threatening or exceeding one's coping responses and options”.

The circumstances that cause stress are called Stressors. Stressors vary in severity and duration the disturbance results from the person's inability to meet the threats posed by the stressor, or from his inadequacy to satisfy the demands by it.

The term 'Acute' refers to sudden onset. Stress of this nature usually involves a rapid response to an abrupt, single, easily identified cause that will often respond positively to some form of intervention (Guyton, 1981; Schuler, 1980).

Chronic stress is a cumulative reaction to a build-up of pressures over a long period of time. This type of response tends to begin gradually and proceed slowly.

Coping refers to the thoughts and actions, an individual use, to deal with threatening situation. Coping refers to, how the mind reacts to stress? Coping refers to thoughts and actions, an individual use, to deal with threatening situation. It is not possible to tolerate stress for long period as it produces feelings of discomfort.

Academic Stress of the students-

The adolescent group is the intermediate group between the dependent childhood and the independent adulthood. This transition from childhood to adulthood is never so easy. Total student population is over 69 million with an expected growth of between 85 and 150,000 every year. Yet they are a neglected group of the population. This group is a vulnerable group to both physical and emotional stress. Due to stress the person may take any steps like in depressions and even suicide. A lot of physical (Increase in the height, Change in voice, Development of secondary sexual characters, Menarche (beginning of menstruation) in girls) and emotional changes (Feeling of independence, Attraction towards opposite sex, Aggressive behavior, Experimenting new things including substance abuse) occur during this period, which are very significant in the shaping a person. According to a many survey, majority of house-holds with a high school or college student have experienced disruptions stemming from COVID-19. A worrisome side effect of these disruptions has been the impact on student mental health. There is need to be sensitive and proactive about reaching vulnerable students who need additional support in terms of technology, housing, or even healthcare.

Review of Literature

In study of Ghosh, Smritikana (2016), academic stress was found to be more prominent among the students of private school than government school. From the findings it may also be

concluded that, female students experienced more academic stress than their male counterparts.

Khaka, (2016) tried to find out various life stressors of adolescents, coping strategies adopted by them and the impact of stress on adolescent mental health. A descriptive, cross sectional study was conducted in the schools in south zone of Delhi, capital city of the country. Data was collected on 360 adolescents. The most frequently used coping strategies by the adolescents were positive reframing, planning, active coping, and instrumental support. It has also been found that stress has a significant impact on adolescent mental health in the form of either internalizing problems such as anxiety, withdrawal and somatic problems or externalizing problems such as rule breaking and aggressive behaviors.

Deb, Sibnath (2016) opined that as academic stress increased, male with high parental support were less likely to be depressed than female. In conclusion, high parental support was related to a reduced risk of depression in female; in male, parental support had a significant moderating effect on the relationship between academic stress and depression.

Bhowmick, Debyani Roy (2017) revealed that high expectations of Teachers/Parents in terms of marks/grades, scolding from Parents/Teachers followed by poor performance, excessive competition, financial problem etc. are the factors causing stress among students.

Fatima Al Rasheed and Atta Abbas Naqvi (2017) in their study revealed that Students studying in health cluster colleges reported high academic stress and self-medication practice. The major stressors identified were examination and course load. Student counselling sessions and counselling by pharmacists regarding self-care may help in the reduction of such stressors and may promote responsible self-medication.

The study of Kaushal (2018) was aimed to find out prevalence of educational stress among school going adolescents and associated factors. In addition to study, the use of stress coping strategies. In this study it is found that 43% children have minimal stress, 56.6% moderate stress, 0.4% have highly stress. Female adolescents have more stress than male. 63% adolescents of government school have moderate stress as compared to private school which has 50.9% moderate stress. The present study reveals that the school going adolescents are having educational stress and which is affected by age, gender, socioeconomic status, examinations, parents expectation and peer and also found that adolescents uses different

coping strategies to cope up with educational stress.

The Study results of Jayashankara Reddy, K., Karishmarajanmenon, M.S., and Anjanathattil (2018) stated that the dimensions of academic stress differed significantly among males and females and fear of failure was the only significant dimension that varied with respect to gender.

Wenjun Chen (2018) noted that social support from family towards was found negatively associated with pressure, workload, and overall academic stress, support from significant other was negatively associated with pressure, despondency, and overall academic stress, while support from friends was negatively associated with pressure among students.

Nagle, Yashwant Kumar and Sharma, Usha (2019). Observed that over a period of time, academic stress among students has increased drastically due to parental expectation and competitive environment among students. This has resulted in having harmful effect to the individual, parents, society and nation at large. In order to overcome such issues, the counsellors and health professionals must take initiative to create awareness among the parents and teachers about their role in fostering a healthy environment.

Parikh, Rachana and Madhuri Krishna (2019) noted that proximal social environments (home, school, peers and neighbourhood) played a major role in causing stress in adolescents' daily lives. Salient social stressors included academic pressure, difficulties in romantic relationships, negotiating parental and peer influences, and exposure to violence and other threats to personal safety.

Xi Lin, Shu Su and Alyssa McElwain (2019) indicated that students' academic self-confidence, confidence for success in their future career, and confidence in making the right academic decisions influence their intentions to actively master the knowledge.

While exploring Stress profile and university performance of pharmacy students, Elham Alshammari (2019) found that no relationship was found between academic performance and academic stress, no correlation between age and academic stress; and a significant relationship was found between the year of study and academic stress.

Becker(2020) studied remote learning practices and difficulties during initial stay-at-home orders during the COVID-19 pandemic in adolescents with and without attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD). Adolescents (238) and parents completed

questionnaires in May/June 2020 when in-person schools were closed in the U.S. Becker concludes that this study provides initial findings of the nature and impact of remote learning during the COVID-19 pandemic. It is imperative for schools and communities to provide the necessary supports to adolescents, particularly those with mental health and/or learning difficulties, and to their parents.

Nitin Joseph and Aneesha Nallapati (2020) indicated that worrying about future and poor self-esteem was independently associated with academic stress among students. Male students adopted more of unhealthy means of coping with academic stress. Therefore, they need to be educated regarding the healthy coping methods.

Michaela C. Pascoe, Sarah E. Hetrick & Alexandra G. Parker (2020) observed that students commonly report high levels of academic related stress, cross-culturally. The academic-related stress experienced by secondary and tertiary students' impacts their mental and physical health and leads to a range of academic problems.

Karel Fromel and Michal Safar (2020) found that adolescents with academic stress are not more physically active after school than adolescents without academic stress represents a warning, they also added that there is a need to seek ways to promote physical activity among adolescents who are at mental health risk.

Siti Fatimah Abdullah¹ and Norliana Ahmad Shah (2020) noted that students feel stress when they do not understand what the lecturer teaches because of a lack of attention in class, when students have a conflict with other students or with their lecturer, it may also cause them to experience stress during their study time, they also added that knowing how to better manage sources of stress helps students experience less stress, allowing them to perform to their fullest potential.

In the study by [Pigaiani](#), Yolande and et.al.(2020) investigated lifestyle behaviors and coping strategies among Italian adolescents, also in relation to the on going COVID-19 pandemic (April1-10,2020). Subjective wellbeing represents a major life goal and is crucial to optimal flourishing and functioning at the psychological, physical, and interpersonal level . In sum, this study focused on adolescents' subjective wellbeing as a function of their lifestyle behaviours and coping strategies. Evidence from this study indicates that with regard to the role played by developmental factors, adolescents' age did not predict any change in subjective

well-being, whereas gender did, with females reporting such a change more likely. Also, both personal and environmental coping resources resulted to be relevant to subjective wellbeing in adolescence, including pursuing different activities such as physical activity on one hand, and receiving family as well as school support on the other.

Chandra (2020) Concluded that Students all over the globe experience stress arising out of many academic as well as non-academic aspects such as environmental, socio-cultural and psychological factors. Stress arises in a way to perform better than peers, to live up to the expectations of parents, teachers, to score better grades which will help to get a dream job. All these put heavy pressure on students leading to a feeling of burnout arising from academic stress, while emotional development starts right from childhood and it affects children in many ways, developing ego concept and his/her emotional and social development.

Mahapatra, Ananya (2020) discussed on Digital learning: an unfamiliar terrain, Greater challenges for students with special needs, The psychological effect of academic stress. The novel coronavirus disease (COVID-19) has been declared by the World Health Organisation as an international public health emergency. India faced total lockdown from 24th March 2020 till today and even though a phased re-opening of public services has since then been attempted, most educational institutions including schools and colleges remain closed without a clear view regarding their re-opening. This has created an unprecedented crisis in the education sector for students as well as educators regarding continuation of educational services, conducting assessments and catering to the needs of special education and vocational rehabilitation.

Stress in Students could be due to many factors such as-

Changing relationship with peers	Changing educational institute
Changing schools	Chronic illness
Covid-19 (Coronavirus outbreak) stress	Financial problems
Death of a loved one	Negative thoughts and feelings
Holiday stress	Pubertal changes
New demands in the educational institute	Safety issues in their neighborhood
Responsibilities to their families	Separation or divorce of parents

Signs and symptoms of stress which include functional adjustments responsible for the stress effects on the body-

Abdominal discomfort	Aggravation of peptic ulcer
Anxiety	Breathlessness
Chest pain	Chronic head ache
Cold clammy skin with gooseflesh	Complain about disorganized
Depend on others	Depletion of energy stores
Depression	Difficult to cope up with work
Difficulty in concentrating	Dry mouth with difficulty in speaking and swallowing
Exacerbation of allergies including asthma	Few Friends
Flare up of diseases like eczema, psoriasis, arthritis	Frozen shoulder
Get angry easily	Headache, back ache and neck pain
Hide feelings	Increased blood glucose levels.
Irritable bowel disease	Loose stools
Loss of appetite	Memory disturbances
Mood swings	Neglect exercise
Outbursts of anger	Over reacting
Palpitation	Signs & symptoms of covid-19
Sleeplessness	Sleeplessness
Substance abuse	Skipping meals
Too little rest	Weight loss

Stress Coping strategies to tackle stress-

Camps	Curl up with a good book
Dance	Eating a healthy diet
Indoor / outdoor games	Manage time better
Meditation	Nature walk
Personal counseling session	Physical exercises
Play with pet	Prayer
Seminars (Online & Offline) to deal with stress	Singing
Students cell	Sweat out tension with a good workout
Team work (at House & Outside)	Watch TV, Comedy, listen music

Work in garden	Workshop on stress management
Writing a their own diary	Yoga

Conclusion-

The education sector in India is one important area that has been severely affected by the lockdown. To cope up with their stress level different innovation programs should be designed for them. Even though they are always under the observation of the teachers, they should not be made aware that they are constantly being observed by the teachers and should not be neglected at all. Legislative and policy measures in the following areas need to make education inclusive and universally accessible to all students e.g. Building professional competency in teachers of regular and special schools in delivering online teaching, Special focus on students from marginalised sections and CWD, Improve penetration of electronic media and internet connectivity across geographical locations and various socio-economic strata, Upscaling of technological infrastructure.

Counsellors in the Educational institutes could be made aware of these categories of students and they must be helped as far as possible. Policy makers in education could be sent a report of the number of students undergoing stress under present scheme of the prescribe curriculum, so that they could make appropriate policy decisions.

Teachers could be provided the names of these students be asked to give them special attention and answer their queries whenever they need Teachers can every now and then be in contact with the parents to know the progress of the students. Parents can be guided by the counselor. Parents if possible could be contacted to provide feedback about their program and made to understand that students is undergoing stream. Some modifications could be deliberately suggested in the home environment. So that parents can be conscious towards what the students is going through. We need to do away with the belief that 'one size fits all' and replace it with the noble thought that there lies strength in diversity. Academicians say a 'drill and kill' approach to curricula has stolen the joy of learning from education. It would teach them not to hide behind a mask of self-doubt or insecurity, but instead learn to take criticism in their stride, not get overwhelmed by feelings and never over-react to stressful situations. The pressing need of the hour is the Educational institutes to design and implement appropriate interventions to alter and enhance students self concept. Educational institutes should adopt

programs like meditation, music, games etc. which would excite the students and they would like to participate in these activities without feeling the fact that they are going through a therapy. Since only small percentage of students, do suffer from high levels of stress. So there should be differential treatment given to these students. Some programs must be assigned separately from these students. So that they can cope up with their stress level.

Out present education scenario is looking only for the intelligent students, their studies, but not on their health, their capacity. Therefore the Educational institutes must provide more help and guidance. Since the aim of education must transcend the development of academic competence, Educational institutes need to become aware of their added responsibility of preparing self-esteemed and fully functioning individuals capable of pursuing their hopes and ambitions, instead of being vulnerable to the devastating effects of examination stress.

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